

The Kulasekarapatnam Rioting Case: An Account of Associated Personalities

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Abstract: *The history of the events that occurred during the August Revolution of 1942 has been recounted at length, but significant gaps remain in its scope. This paper attempts to address one such gap in the case of the Kulasekarapatnam Rioting Case, an event that took place in the Madras Province, by providing an account of the persons involved and the punishments inflicted on them by the judiciary. It also accounts for the advocates who argued on their behalf and on behalf of the government, the kin of the deceased British official, the local and national-level leaders and freedom fighters who helped the nationalists during their legal battle against the death sentence. By bringing out such details, the paper seeks to expand the historiography of the subject and documents the personnel who revolved around the event.*

Keywords: *August Revolution (1942), Kulasekarapatnam Rioting Case, Quit India Movement in Tamil Nadu, Historiography of the August Revolution, Nationalism and Capital Punishment, Revolutionary Nationalism*

Introduction

The August Revolution of 1942, a historic event during the Quit India Movement, has been widely recounted in academic circles, and many previously unknown regional-level incidents have also emerged over the years. Since most such works were pioneers in the subject, their scope was largely limited to narrating the incident, its causes, the resulting outcomes, and its overall impact on the nationalist movement. Only very few works, however, delve into the details of the personalities associated with these incidents, those who were not participants themselves, but rather regional-level and national-level leaders and freedom fighters who supported the personnel involved in the incident, thereby expanding the ambit of the scholarship.

This paper, along with a brief history of the event to provide context, seeks to account for the details of such persons who, though not participants, were closely associated with the incident that later came to be known as the Kulasekarapatnam Rioting Case. By providing such an account, the paper aims to widen knowledge of the subject and enhance the historiography of the topic, as such widened scope is believed to be helpful for future scholarship on the subject.

Kulasekarapattinam Rioting Case – A Brief History

After the failure of Cripps mission, Mahatma Gandhi famously proclaimed 'Do or Die', and with that, the Quit India Movement began. With the arrest of all top-level leaders, no proper command structure existed for the cadres and the people, which resulted in the rise of violent revolutionary activities across the nation. The month of August and September witnessed many such incidents.

Tirunelveli District of the Madras Province, which had always been a hotspot for nationalist movement since the days of Swadeshi Movement, was no exception. The taluk of Tiruchendur in Tirunelveli District was even more daunting as burning police, postal and railway stations, cutting off telegraph wires and destroying public property had become the order of the day. During these events, the most

unfortunate incident was the Assassination of the Assistant Inspector of Salt of Kulasekarapattinam, Mr. Wilfred Loane. The nationalists of the taluk had planned to storm the salt pan and the office of the British Salt Department to loot weapons. However, when they came across the Assistant Inspector of Salt, chaos ensued. When the British officer began to attack the nationalists, they retaliated, and eventually the officer was killed. This incident, which occurred on 20 September 1942, later came to be known as the 'Kulashekarapatnam Rioting Case' (Sivasubramanian 35-44).

The incident caused huge uproar in the taluk. The Malabar Special Police (M.S.P), a punitive police force, were deployed to apprehend the nationalists involved. The police force molested and harassed many nationalists and ordinary people and arrested around 115 individuals (Mandiram 105) during the investigation, most of whom had nothing to do with the incident but had supported the nationalist cause. Among those arrested were not only ordinary civilians but village officials who had taken part in the freedom struggle, such as R. Venkatrama Mudaliar, the Karnam of Kayalpattinam (Kamarasu 517), and Narayana Nadar, the Munsif of Nathankinaru (Ganapathi 12).

After some time, 26 persons were placed before the court as the final accused in the case. The First two accused Rajagopalan and Kasirajan were sentenced to death, while a few others received life imprisonment and ordinary imprisonment and some were acquitted (Sivasubramanian 42). The two death penalty awardees had carried out a long legal battle, which finally resulted in their release in 1946 after the formation of Interim Government (Ganapathiraman 66).

Associated Figures and Their Roles

The 26 accused men – listed in the order in which they appear in the judgement, along with their respective punishments, are as follows (Mandiram 107-108):

1. Mr. Rajagopalan – Death Penalty
2. Mr. Kasirajan – Death Penalty
3. Mr. A.S Benjamin – Life Sentence
4. Mr. R. Chelladurai – Life Sentence
5. Mr. K. Ponnaiah Nadar – Acquitted
6. Mr. P. Narayana Pillai – Five years' imprisonment
7. Mr. T. Dharmamkovil Pillai – Life Sentence
8. Mr. Rathnaswamy alias Perumal Nadar – Acquitted
9. Mr. Maharaja Nadar – Acquitted
10. Mr. Deviyiraka Nadar – Ten years' imprisonment
11. Mr. Thangaiyah Nadar – Life Sentence
12. Mr. Arumuga Nadar – Acquitted
13. Mr. Kani Nadar – Acquitted
14. Mr. Chelladurai – Acquitted
15. Mr. Narayanan – Acquitted
16. Mr. Nellaiyappa Servai – Acquitted
17. Mr. Sivanthakani alias Muthumaalai Nadar – Life Sentence
18. Mr. Thangaswamy Nadar – Acquitted
19. Mr. Motta Alias Rathnaswamy – Two years' imprisonment
20. Mr. Poovalinga Nadar – Two years' imprisonment
21. Mr. Lakshmanan – Acquitted
22. Mr. Thangaiyah alias Aasirvadha Nadar – Acquitted

23. Mr. Kasi Nadar – Acquitted
24. Mr. Duraiswamy Nadar – Kept as Detenu
25. Mr. Lakshmana Nadar – Kept as Detenu
26. Mr. Mandirakon – Life Sentence

Kin of the Deceased British official – The Collector of Salt Revenue, Madras, visited the village after the event and reported his observations to Mr. J.F. Sheeh, member of Central Board of Revenue, on 27 September 1942. From his report the details of the kin of the deceased are revealed. Mr. Wilfred Loane, an ex-soldier and a European of Irish Patronage, was a bachelor. He had two sisters, who were either widowed or separated from their husbands, and a brother who was an engineer residing in Bangalore. Mr. Loane was the one who supported his sisters, and his death caused huge loss to them. The Collector of Salt revenue recommended that the board grant a suitable allowance to the dependents of the deceased and bear the costs of his funeral (Revenue 46).

The souvenir released by the Freedom Fighters Association of Tiruchendur Taluk claims that the sisters of Mr. Wilfred Loane also petitioned the government to show mercy to the first two accused who were on death row (Ganapathi 17).

The Police Officials – The case was investigated and handled by the police officials of the village of Kulasekarapatnam. Mr. Ramalingam Pillai was the then Sub-Inspector of Police of Kulasekarapatnam (Mandiram 105). He was also a close friend of the deceased Assistant Inspector of Salt, Mr. Wilfred Loane. Even on that fateful night, Mr. Loane had visited Mr. Ramalingam Pillai and had a long conversation with him before returning to his quarters, hours before his assassination (Sivasubramanian 36). The Deputy Superintendent of Police at that time was Mr. Appadurai Pillai, who was stationed at the village of Srivaikuntam. He, along with the Sub-Inspector, went to the village to assess the situation only after a week, since the nationalists involved in the case had looted many weapons and were on the run; fearing them, the police waited until some weapons were recovered from a village well. After this, the Malabar Special Police were deployed to avoid any confrontations and to maintain law and order, as such terror prevailed in the region (Mandiram 105).

Judiciary – After the arrest, the first and second accused were produced before the Special Judge of Tirunelveli, Mr. P.V. Balakrishna Ayyar, who, in Special Criminal Courts Ordinance Case No 1 of 1942, ordered the death sentence on 06 February 1943 (Sivasubramanian 43). The two, Mr. Rajagopalan and Mr. Kasirajan, who were sentenced to death, appealed before the High Court of Madras in Case No 60 of 1943, where Mr. Justice Archibald John King and Mr. Justice M. Shahabuddin confirmed the sentence of the lower court (A.N 169). Further, both of them appealed before the Federal Court in Rajagopalan and Another Vs the King Emperor, in which a three-judge bench headed by Chief Justice Sir Patrick Spens, along with Justice Sir Muhammed Zafrulla Khan and Justice Sir Srinivasa Varadachariar, heard the case. The first two upheld the death sentence, while the latter delivered a separate judgement stating that he found it difficult to sustain the majority's decision. On the whole, the majority judgement upheld the death sentence (Rajagopalan and Another Versus the King Emperor).

Advocates – The advocates who argued for the total 26 convicts in the Kulasekarapatnam Rioting Case before the Special Judge of Tirunelveli were Mr. A.S Ramanjuam (appeared for the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 5th, 7th, 11th, 12th, 16th and 22nd accused), Mr. A.V Desikachariar (appeared for the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 5th, 7th, 11th, 12th, 16th and 22nd

accused) Mr. K.S. Balaji (appeared for the 1st, 7th, 11th, 22nd and 24th accused), Mr. S.P Sivasubramaniya Nadar (appeared for the 2nd, 3rd and 5th accused) Mr. Daniel Thomas (who later become a minister in the state of Tamil Nadu, appeared for the 4th, 6th, 8th, 9th, 10th, 13th, 14th, 15th, 17th, 18th, 19th, 20th, 25th and 26th accused), Mr. S.P. Rajendran (appeared for the 4th, 6th, 8th, 9th, 10th, 13th and 14th accused), Mr. V.S. Sankarasubramaniya Mudaliar (appeared for the 12th and 16th accused), Mr. Chellapandiyan (who later became the speaker of Tamil Nadu State Legislative Assembly, appeared for the 15th, 17th, 18th, 19th, 20th, 25th and 26th accused), Mr. T.R. Ganapathirama Iyer (appeared for the 21st accused), Mr. T.M Subramanian (appeared for the 21st accused) and Mr. T.V Ramasesha Iyer (who appeared for the 23 accused Mr. kasi Nadar, for whom alone the government had arranged the advocate) (Mandiram 107-108).

In the Federal Court, the first two convicts, Mr. Rajagopalan and Mr. Kasirajan, were represented by Mr. M.C. Sridharan, against the Advocate-General of Madras, Sir Alladi Krishnaswami Aiyar, who was also a member of the drafting committee of the Indian Constituent Assembly and was held in high regard by Babasaheb Ambedkar, appearing on behalf of the Crown, assisted by Mr. N. Rajagopala Iyengar. Sir Brojendra Mitter, Advocate-General of India along with H. K. Bose, appeared for the Governor-General in Council (Rajagopalan and Another Versus the King Emperor).

Freedom Fighters and Leaders who helped – When the death sentence of the first two convicts were upheld by the Federal court, their families did not know what to do next. Until then, they had been assisted by M.C. Veerabahu Pillai (Venkatakrishnan 355), a veteran freedom fighter who had taken part in many national movements and had been imprisoned several times (Nadu 155). He was also the president of Tuticorin District Congress Committee and later a member of the constituent assembly and also a Member of Parliament. Mr. M.C. Veerabahu Pillai then asked the families to approach Mr. Venkatakrishnan, alias Kittu, and sent him a letter explaining the circumstances (Venkatakrishnan 355). Mr. Venkatakrishnan, was also a veteran freedom fighter who had taken part in many nationalist initiatives and was an ardent congressman (Somayajulu 306). He understood the situation and wrote to Mahatma Gandhi seeking his help, citing the latter's role in assisting the nationalists involved in the Chimur-Ashti episode (Venkatakrishnan 355). Mahatma Gandhi then asked C. Rajagopalachari to intervene in the matter to help the two nationalists. Also, in a reply to a letter written by one T.N Avinashilingam, whether he was the well-known T.S. Avinashilingam Chettiar - a prominent Gandhian from Tamil Nadu, is not known, Gandhi stated that the case should be taken further to the Privy Council and enquired about the cost of such an endeavour and assistance that would be required (Gandhi 177). Later, Rajaji, after hearing from Gandhi, met Mr. Venkatakrishnan, enquired about the details, asked him to procure a legal draft from an advocate that could be filed in the Privy Council (Venkatakrishnan 356). And he took care of the required finances by issuing advertisements in magazines, thereby starting a campaign to raise funds, which was estimated at around 10,000 Rupees (Venkatakrishnan 356). Venkatakrishnan sought the help of Mr. R. Venkatraman, who later became the President of India, to draft a legal petition to be filed before the Privy Council (Venkatakrishnan 356). As per an advertisement issued in the newspaper The Hindu on 02 November 1944 by Rajaji, S.N. Ambalavanam Pillai of Sankarankovil (Rajagopalachari 286-287) was the person to whom Rajaji had asked the collected funds to be remitted. Mr.

S.N. Ambalavanam Pillai was the President of Sankarankovil Taluk Congress Committee and Secretary of Tirunelveli District Congress Committee (Somayajulu 264), as well as a veteran freedom fighter (Nadu 112).

On the whole M.C Veerabahu Pillai, Venkatakrishnan, S.N. Ambalavana Pillai, T.N. Avinashilingam were among the regional level leaders and freedom fighters who offered their support. Mahatma Gandhi, Rajaji, R. Venkatraman were among the national-level leaders who extended their assistance to the nationalists.

Out of all these, Rajaji played a pivotal role in securing the release of the first two convicts. At first, he thought that appealing further to the Privy Council would help, but later he felt that Privy Council would never overturn the Federal Court judgements in most cases, so the best thing to try was to approach the Viceroy with a mercy petition. The family and Venkatakrishnan left the decision to the wisdom of Rajaji. Rajaji then filed a mercy petition and got the death sentence commuted to life. After the formation of the Interim Government in 1946, those two were released (Venkatakrishnan 357).

Conclusion

These were the diverse range of personalities who revolved around the incident. Understanding the roles of these individuals would elaborate on the nature of the movement and also help expand the dimensions of the historiography of the subject.

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